

CHANGES IN THE PSYCHOHYGIENE OF STUDENTS DURING EDUCATIONAL COURSES AND THEIR CORRECTION

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Abstract. This article discusses changes in students' psychological hygiene during training courses and issues of their correction.

Keywords: psychohygiene, student, mental factor, socialization, stereotype.

ИЗМЕНЕНИЯ ПСИХОГИГИЕНЫ СТУДЕНТОВ В ПРОЦЕССЕ ОБУЧЕНИЯ И ИХ КОРРЕКЦИЯ

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются изменения психогигиены студентов в процессе обучения и вопросы их коррекции.

Ключевые слова: психогигиена, студент, психический фактор, социализация, стереотип.

Psychohygiene is recognized as a science that identifies factors that negatively affect a person's mental (spiritual) and nervous system, develops measures to protect and develop his mental health.

One of the main tasks of modern mental hygiene is to constantly study and promote healthy thinking, analyze one's problems and form correct conclusions, learn the causes of pathogenic or illogical thoughts and ways to eliminate them.

During the student period, which is the first stage of maturity, the age of 17-20 years is especially characterized by psychological complexity.

On the one hand, high school the student has weak goals and motives characteristic of a vocational college student, insufficiently formed responsibility for himself, on the other hand, the desire to adapt to a new environment and independence. and enthusiasm is growing rapidly.
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The student period is not limited to the acquisition of necessary professional knowledge and skills, it is the period of a person's pursuit of perfection; All mental processes are activated in the student (memory, imagination, thinking, etc.). The student develops actively in cultural, spiritual (including moral), physical, aesthetic and other aspects. With the realization of the real "I" in the personality of the student, the desire for the ideal "I" increases.

As a result of the strengthening of the ego, the desire for independence and responsibility for one's actions increases. Socialization of a student's personality is one of the components of personality socialization and also has the following content and essence.

Under the influence of the social environment, a person receives the knowledge and experience necessary for his life, work and activities. But humanthe'zi does not mechanically accept the accumulated social knowledge and life experience, but actively creatively approaches and changes them. In addition, the social environment is rapidly changing and dynamic. Consequently,the'a growing person should be flexible, alert, flexible (elastic) to master the values, norms and attitudes of society. Only the process of socialization with this ability is enough.

I. Socialization - of the individualthe'zi is the ability to join the society in which he lives, to master the cultural and spiritual rules and laws, to show them in his behavior, behavior and activities, accepting the norms, requirements and values of the society.

Socialization is a person's continuous knowledge of the social world, and in human relationships he manifests his individuality in a way that cannot be duplicated by others.

Socialization has the following content and components:

Acquisition of culture in the process of socialization. Manthe'In the process of growth and development, he accepts the culture of his nation and people. Every nationthe'He conveys his accumulated knowledge, culture, faith, art, traditions, etc. to the next generation. Human cultural development continues from birth to the end of life. M. Herskovits divides the process of assimilation of a person's culture into his society and society into 2 stages.

1. The period of active learning of language, social norms, cultural and spiritual values during childhood, adolescence and youth.
2. The period of assimilation of new ideas, inventions, discoveries during the life and activities of adults.

If at the first stage a person gradually accepts the components of culture, at the second stage the selection and creative processing of the acquired ideas takes place.

Culture from generation to generation in society and societythe'teeth are divided into three types.

1. Vertical - values, skills, beliefs are passed from parents to children.
2. Horizontal - cultural traditions, customs and social experience are acquired through communication with peers in the process of personal development.
3. Indirect - cultural experience and knowledge obtained in special educational institutions (school, college, institute) and from people close to oneself (relatives, friends, neighbors) are different.

II. The assimilation of social culture in the process of socialization is called interiorization. This happens in two ways.

1. Acquiring national, universal values and patterns of behavior.
2. Social importance; symbols, values, institutions, acceptance in the educational process.

III. A concept close to socialization - the process of adaptation to the social environment and its disruption (appropriate adaptation) plays an important role in human life.

People are attentive to others, responsible, independent people adapt quickly and easily to the social environment. Uncultured, apathetic, selfish individuals find it difficult to adapt to the social environment.

In addition to the process of socialization, the following events affecting the life and activities of a person in society can be noted.

1. Social comfort - a person performs tasks and tasks under the control of other people better, becomes active.

2. Social inhibition - a person slows down the performance of tasks and assignments under the control of another person.

This is social thinking - team members agree on positive or negative decisions for the purpose of cooperation, solidarity and empathy for the team. The most important thing is to join the majority and come to an opinion as soon as possible.

3. Team Conflicts Team disputes and arguments can lead to team members coming to conflicting opinions rather than consensus.

4. Social stereotypes - inadequate, unfair assessment of the surrounding people and stereotypical thinking about them. For example: "Caucasians are bad, Gypsies are thieves" and so on.

Such thoughts arise due to the following circumstances.

- If a person does not want to do a deep and comprehensive analysis.
- The reason why a person does not want to study people is that he does not have time, opportunity and desire.

- When a person is nervous, excited, tired.

- When a person is busy with other things

5. Human human values, norms and experiences only and only in society they will try It provides social experience by interacting with other people and receives social experience from them. Man is under the positive influence of society.

6. If the group and community are criminal and socially alienated, then such a community has a negative effect on the individual.

In the educational process, attention should be paid to the following characteristics of students in the field of mental hygiene and their correction:

1. Development of observational skills. Forming the ability to see things and events around us that others do not see or understand. If you pay attention, great inventors have this ability. Geniuses like Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Farabi, H. Columbus Humanity is grateful

to them for their discoveries, which they felt, but did not understand their inner essence.

For example, many people feel better in winter, when it snows and when the cold starts, than at other times of the year. Diseases related to ventilation are drastically reduced. It is believed that this phenomenon is caused by the effect of cold and snow, which weakens the activity of various microbes and viruses. In fact, this is not the case, the human body activates all its systems to adapt to the cold, and the clearing of the air with snowfall leads to a decrease in diseases. Theoretical and practical exercise it is possible to reveal unique aspects of things and events that have not yet been taken into account by conducting them in the form of a problem-based lesson.

2. Creative thinking is highly developed during adolescence. But the youth, the student period is not an exception to this process, because the student has regular and continuous knowledge and acquires skills, positive changes occur in his central nervous system and thinking. Creativity among students

have a desire to do. He is interested in various fields, writes poems and stories, it is a task of state importance to identify these interests among students in a timely manner, to organize methodical support for them. Creative thinking students have the following characteristics: a wealth of ideas and new ideas, these students are interested in various fields and their research areas are also broad. These students need a mentor to guide their interest and exploration.

3. The majority of students are young people with real leadership and organizational skills. They are enterprising, hardworking and hardworking. By developing these skills, we ensure that future leaders grow with vision and creativity.

4. Problems related to the independent acquisition of knowledge and skills are of great importance in the student's activity today.

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